

School literacy movement program in elementary school, Indonesia: Literature review

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ABSTRACT

The Ministry of Education and Culture developed the school literacy movement (SLM) program. This program aims to foster student interest in reading and improve reading skills so that knowledge can be mastered better. The author uses a literature review design by collecting data from various journal sources relevant to the SLM program in elementary schools, Indonesia. This research is an analytical descriptive study, which is a regular breakdown of the data that has been obtained, then understanding and explanation are given so that it can be understood well by the reader. The selected journal criteria are journals published in 2015-2021. SLM activities in elementary schools are influenced by supporting and inhibiting factors. The supporting factor is that the principal has a good commitment to carry out SLM activities, teachers and students and other components of the school also contribute to the success of SLM activities in elementary schools. Availability of sufficient funds to provide the necessary books is also a factor supporting SLM. While the inhibiting factor is that there are still very few books available so students cannot choose reading books that match their interests. Reading books is the main factor that must exist to make this SLM activity a success. Therefore, the procurement of reading books is very necessary. Students' reading habits are still low, they are still waiting for the teacher's orders to carry out SLM activities. The SLM schedule is not fully for 15-minute reading activities as specified in the manual. Lack of parental involvement in SLM activities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Educational practices need to make schools a learning organization so that all its citizens grow as lifelong learners. School literacy movement (SLM) is conducted around the world. Finland is a country that makes reading a culture. The activity is supported by a library that is divided into public libraries and university libraries throughout Finland located in rural or small towns. The Netherlands seeks to grow children's reading interest through the obligation to read books every morning before starting lessons and the afternoon before returning home. In addition, schools in the Netherlands also make regular agenda visits to public libraries. Swedish people have a high interest in reading seen from the public libraries scattered in a number of crowded points such as shopping centers and train stations. In Stockholm alone there are 51 public libraries to serve a population of only 2.3 million. The number of books that can be borrowed by each person

reaches 50 books with a loan period of six weeks. Australia strives to foster an early reading culture by giving books in parcel packages to families who have just had a baby. It was first implemented by the state of New South Wales in January 2019 followed by the state of Victoria in July 2019 [1]–[3].

The Ministry of Education and Culture developed the SLM. SLM strengthens the movement for ethical growth as stated in regulation of the minister of education and culture no. 23 of 2015. One of the activities in the movement is the activity of 15 minutes of reading non-learning books before the start of study time. This activity is carried out to foster students' reading interest and improve reading skills so that knowledge can be mastered better. Reading material contains ethical values, in the form of local, national, and global wisdom delivered according to the stage of student development. This important breakthrough should involve all stakeholders in the field of education, ranging from the central, provincial, district/city levels, to education units. The involvement of parents and the community is also an important component in SLM.

Another indicator that led the government to launch the SLM is that there is international research that concludes that Indonesia is at a low order in terms of literacy. The literacy ability of the younger generation in Indonesia is still very low. According to the results of the test in grade four elementary school by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) in the progress in international reading literacy study (PIRLS) in 2011, it was stated that Indonesia ranked 45th out of 48 participating countries with a score of 428 out of an average score of 500. Then, according to a survey conducted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2015 it was mentioned that Indonesia ranks 65th out of 72 countries [1], [4], [5].

In addition, based on the results of a survey conducted by United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) to the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) countries in 2011, it was obtained that Indonesia was ranked at the lowest rating with a score of 0.001. This data shows that out of about 1,000 Indonesians only one has a high reading culture [1]. Based on these low performances, the ministry of education issued ministerial regulation no. 23 of 2015 on the growth of ethics in which it is expressed about the habituation of literacy culture. Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture (Permendikbud) then gave birth to the SLM which is a program to make the school environment with literate citizens [2], [6].

SLM is a comprehensive and ongoing effort to make the school a learning organization whose citizens are literate throughout life through public engagement. SLM aims to create fun and child-friendly eco-program where all its citizens show empathy, care, a spirit of curiosity and love of knowledge, are able to communicate and can contribute to their social environment. The participation of school residents (teachers, principals, students, parents, education personnel, school supervisors, and school committees) academics, businesses and industry and stakeholders under the coordination of the directorate general of primary and secondary education of the ministry of education, culture, research and technology.

SLM has two purposes: i) General purpose and ii) Special purpose. The general purpose of SLM is to develop the ethics of learners through the cultivation of the school literacy ecosystem embodied in SLM so that they become lifelong learners. Furthermore, in particular, the objectives of SLM are: i) Fostering a culture of literacy in schools; ii) Improving the capacity of residents and school environments to be literate; iii) Making the school a fun and child-friendly learning park so that school residents are able to manage knowledge; and iv) Maintaining the sustainability of learning by presenting a variety of reading books and accommodating various reading strategies [7]–[9].

The implementation of SLM has three stages, namely, the habituation stage, the development stage, and the learning stage. The habituation stage aims to foster students' interest in reading material and reading activities. Next, the development stage, literacy activities at the development stage aims to maintain interest in reading and reading activities, as well as improve the smoothness and learner's reading comprehension.

In the third stage, which is the learning stage, the purpose of this stage is to maintain students' interest in reading and reading activities, as well as improve students' literacy skills through enrichment books and textbooks. SLM activities are conducted for the first 15 minutes before the lesson begins. This activity is filled with reading activities. SLM activities in elementary schools are recommended that teachers apply various types of reading activities such as read aloud, sustained silent reading (SSR), guided reading, shared reading, and independent reading [8]. After the regulation on SLM is running, there are various researches that evaluate its implementation. Therefore, the author will conduct a literature review on the implementation of SLM program in elementary school, in Indonesia.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The author uses a literature review design by collecting data from various journal sources relevant to the SLM program in elementary schools, Indonesia. Literature review is a systematic, explicit and

reproducible method for identifying, evaluating and synthesizing research works and ideas that have been produced by researchers and practitioners. This research is an analytical descriptive study, which is a regular breakdown of the data that has been obtained, then understanding and explanation are given so that it can be understood well by the reader. The selected journal criteria are journals published in 2015-2021. The author uses a descriptive qualitative approach to discuss the implementation of the SLM program in elementary schools, Indonesia.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The implementation of school literacy movement program

Ardian [10] said SLM should be able to make students love reading first rather than being given many tasks that will make students bored. In addition, the government should also pay attention to the availability of school facilities related to SLM such as the state of the library and its book collection so that students can read many reading books, while cooperation and support committee school is also needed in order for the purpose of SLM to be achieved to the maximum. Here's the implementation of SLM program in Indonesia. In general, the term literacy means the ability of individuals to process and understand information while reading or writing. SLM is more than just reading and writing but it includes thinking skills according to the stages and components of literacy [11].

Many studies were conducted in connection with the SLM activities. Previous researches examined the influence of SLM to increase students' reading interest [12]–[14]. Meanwhile, researchers [15], [16] conducted research on the pattern of literacy activities in students' thematic books and patterns of literacy activities at the elementary school level. Then Lastiningsih et al. conducted research on 48 principals in Sidoarjo related to managing SLM management in their respective schools. While five other studies took the topic of SLM implementation based on supporting activities, supporting factors, and inhibitory factors [17]–[22].

SLM activities are carried out in the morning, after finishing praying. The class teacher instructs students to start reading. Some students rushed to find the book they wanted to read on the bookshelf. They are trying to find the same book they have not finished reading. When they got the book, they were looking for, they looked happy. Some of the other students left their seats reluctantly and took whatever books were left with surrender. Nevertheless, each student reads diligently in their own seats. They read in SSR.

The school also prepares non textbooks for each class. Various non-textbooks play an important role in influencing students' interest in reading. The book for reading activities is provided by the school and it is adjusted to the class level and is equated to the number of students in the class. The book is placed on a bookshelf provided by the school and stored in the corner of the classroom [23]. Through reading, a child is expected to be able to imitate positive things in the story or book he has read.

At Elementary School Dharma Karya Universitas Terbuka, Banten, Indonesia also announced *tausiyah* (Islamic discourse/speech) on Friday as an SLM activity. In this activity, students in each class listened to the *tausiyah* of one of the teachers centrally (broadcast from the announcement room). After completing *tausiyah*, students are asked to make a summary of the *tausiyah* they heard in their respective books [24].

State Elementary School 2 Sitirejo and State Elementary School 4 Panggungrejo in Malang District, Indonesia became the implementing schools of SLM in the school showed that: i) Facilities for SLM activities such as libraries, reading corners and wall magazines in two schools have had although some classes do not have a special reading and wall magazines angle and some are not yet complete have such facilities; ii) Not many students are seen using library facilities and reading corners, the reading corner is impressed only used in reading activities before learning; and iii) Canteens and other schoolyards do not display motivational text and positive invitations as one of the characteristics of a literate school environment.

3.2. The supporting of school literacy movement factors

The supporting of SLM factors in elementary school is depending on the principal's commitment to implement Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture (Permendikbud) no. 23 of 2015 on SLM. An activity will be carried out properly when the supreme leader in the institution has a commitment to carry it out. The motivation of the principal and the spirit of the teachers in carrying out SLM activities are excellent. The existence of reading corner facilities and wall magazines made by the school and the school library, donated books from parents of students and trusted to be a reference school related to SLM by the district education office [25]–[27].

Supportive school community, teachers, and students support the implementation of SLM at elementary school. They carry out SLM according to the schedule made by the school. Students voluntarily

bring books from home for SLM activities, teachers try to read the storybooks available in their classrooms in order to help students understand the stories they read.

Students' enthusiasm participated in this SLM activity. Since the existence of SLM students' reading interest has increased. To increase student's interest in reading is not easy; it takes a long time and support from various parties so that it is expected to be a culture in elementary school students. The benefit of SLM is to add insight and literacy skills of elementary school students.

The effort in making a reading corner, wall magazine, and school library will support literacy in school. Reading points and wall magazines can be placed in the classroom or outside the classroom. The number of books available in the library is also a supporting factor of SLM. Parents can become book donors. The reading material presented can be fiction and nonfiction books. Sufficient funds are available for book procurement. Some elementary schools are very lucky because they have sufficient funds for the procurement of books. This is in contrast to research conducted by Rohman [20] which states that lack of funds is one of the obstacles to the success of SLM.

3.3. The inhibiting of school literacy movement factors

Director general of primary and secondary education of the Minister of Education and Culture, Lastiningsih *et al.* [27] stated that there are three problems faced in the implementation of SLM nationally, namely the first, the lack of availability of reading books in its main schools in remote areas of the country. Second, teachers do not yet fully understand the methods or techniques that will be used in improving the culture of literacy. Third, the lack of available reading places, such as libraries, reading corners, and so on that supports the implementation of SLM activities.

An inadequate book for school. Books in each class are not yet eligible for the implementation of SLM activities either from the point of view of the number or seen from the type of books available. The number of books available is still very limited and not varied. This limitation can be a factor to inhibit students from wanting to read books because the available books are not in accordance with their interests. The books in the classroom are only a few students. Similarly, to its kind makes students bored to read the books provided in school and try to bring their own books. This is in line with previous researchers [13], [19], [23], [27], [28] which state that the procurement of library materials or reading books is one of the obstacles in the success of the SLM program.

Students are not used to reading. The lack of interest in students to read is because reading activities do not become a habit since childhood that brought up by parents at home. Although students already know the literacy schedule because every day is done, they have not moved from their seats to look for books until the class teacher reminds them that it is time to read a book. This could be because they have no interest in it. According to Faradina [13] and Rohman [20] interest in reading can be interpreted as a tendency to continue reading because of the urge in students to find out the information needed. Research conducted by Agustin and Cahyono [12] also concluded that the students in the research object have a cultural background that is far from the culture of literacy so that this becomes a factor in inhibiting the success of SLM. Rohman [20] said that the involvement of parents and the community became an important component in the success of SLM. State Elementary School 4 Panggungrejo in implementing SLM is a lack of passion for reading students, difficult schools to increase the level of activities, teachers lack focus on running this activity and lack of guidance from the education office both at the sub-district and district levels. SLM activities aim to encourage students to like to read and develop interests in accordance with their potential talents to expand the horizons of life in developing themselves [29]. Thus, the school should create a focused schedule for SLM activities so that the habituation of reading books and critical thinking can be developed well [30], [31].

Unavailable library room in school; the case occurred at State Elementary School 2 Sitirejo, namely the submission of a book proposal to the education office, the proposal for library procurement to the education office has long been done until 2017, low-grade reading techniques are alternated using techniques read aloud so that students concentrate during reading activities. The most important obstacles to the implementation of SLM at State Elementary School 2 Sitirejo are the facilities related to SLM and reading books as infrastructure for reading activities, while State Elementary School 4 Panggungrejo further reveals the quality of SLM activities and students' reading interests. Parents are somewhat indifferent to their children's needs. By making parents as donors of reading books that are emphasized to students who get low grades during daily replays and each one student brings one book from home at the end of each even semester can be a solution for parents' involvement in the development of child literacy.

4. CONCLUSION

Elementary school in Indonesia, the school has seriously prepared SLM as evidenced by the establishment of SLM activity coordinators, the preparation of SLM activity schedules, and the preparation of reading books for each class. SLM activities in elementary school are influenced by supporting factors and

inhibitory factors. The supporting factor that appears is that the principal has a good commitment to carry out SLM activities, teachers and students and other components of the school also contribute to the success of SLM activities in elementary school. The availability of sufficient funds to provide the necessary books is also a supporting factor of SLM. While the inhibitory factor is still very low number of books available so that students cannot choose a reading book that suits their interests. Reading books are the main factors that must exist for the success of the purpose of this SLM activity. Therefore, the procurement of reading books is indispensable. Students' reading habits are still low, still waiting for the teacher's orders to do SLM activities. The SLM schedule is not yet fully for the 15-minute reading activity as specified in the manual. Lack of parental involvement in SLM activities, parental support either in provision of books and permission for students spend their time in library still insufficient.

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